

Bachelor's Degree in Computer Engineering

EI1048 – Software Paradigms

SEMINAR 2

AI-Based User Story Co-Creation Workshop

Objectives:

1. Evaluate the potential of AI in exploring functional spaces (user needs).
2. Creative use of AI considering criteria of usefulness, value/cost, and applicability.

Application Context

The goal is to develop an application called “Supermarket Comparator” which, given a shopping list, returns recommendations on where to buy each product in order to maximize savings, together with the total cost of the list (according to the recommendations).

Working Methodology

1. Download the report template (.docx format) that you must submit at the end of the class through the Virtual Classroom (VC).
2. Choose a free, general-purpose generative AI tool.
3. Providing the application context and its purpose, request from the AI an initial proposal of user stories (US). Write your request in a direct but formal manner. If you consider it necessary, refine your request and ask again.
4. Make an initial overall assessment of the response: Is it well organized? Original? Realistic? Risky? Incomplete? Inconsistent? Redundant? Justify your answer (9–10 lines).
5. What changes would you introduce in the initial proposal of user stories? What new stories would you add? Which ones would you modify? Which ones would you remove?
6. In a new request, ask the AI to provide the list of user stories in a spreadsheet, so that each user story appears in one row. Ask the AI to include columns to evaluate “User value,” “Value/Cost ratio,” “Feasibility” (the opposite of risk), and “Justification” (for the scores). Assign a numerical value between 1 (very low) and 5 (very high) to each criterion, and use the “justification” column to explain your decisions.
7. Considering the user stories suggested by the AI, the assigned scores, and possible omissions and inconsistencies (item 4), make a justified proposal of a set of user stories

(scope) to be potentially integrated into a first version of the app to be launched on the market in 3 months.

8. Ask the AI to identify and characterize 3 potential user profiles. Analyze the response.
9. Considering the scope (item 3) and one of the user profiles (item 8), ask the AI for new usability user stories that we should consider to improve the user experience (UX).
10. Add these new usability user stories to the spreadsheet, and update your proposal for the app scope to be delivered in 3 months (in a different color). Justify your decisions.
11. Write, as conclusions, final reflections on this activity.
12. Before the end of the class, one of the authors must submit/upload the report and the spreadsheet (item 6) through this VC activity.

Assessment Criteria

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Assessment Criteria

The seminar grade will be the sum of the evaluation of 5 sections:

Dimension	Assessment Item	Score (2-Yes, 1-Partial, 0-No)	Comments
1. Transparency and honesty	Interactions with AI are documented (what, when, for what purpose).		
	The contributions of the AI and those of the team are clearly distinguished.		
2. Relevance and added value	The use of AI provides real value to the project (e.g., needs, unique scenarios, etc.).		
	It is justified why those contributions are relevant.		
3. Critical analysis	Errors, biases, or limitations in the AI's responses are identified.		
	Decisions made based on the analysis are corrected and documented.		
4. Integration with learning	The use of AI contributed to learning or to achieving the objectives of the exercise.		
	The decisions made are linked to the objectives of the course.		
5. Creativity and exploration	Multiple alternatives of requirements and usage scenarios are explored with AI.		
	The best options are critically selected and discarded options are justified.		